

1 Title:

2 Indicating landslide hazard from tree rings – ecosystem service provided by an alder forest in
3 the Hengduan Mts, Sichuan, China

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21
22 Abstract:

23 Landslides are destructive geomorphological processes that cause economic and social losses.
24 This stimulates the development of new tools related to landslide hazard. Recently, trees, their
25 growth rings and dendrochronology have become widely used in landslide studies. Thus, this
26 study aims to explore the potential of trees in providing landslide-monitoring ecosystem
27 services through dendrochronology. In our opinion, establishing such an idea would help
28 promote empirical evidence on the efficiency of tree-ring-based tools to decision-makers. We
29 use the example of a landslide in the Moxi basin, Sichuan, China and present results of
30 dendrochronological analysis of growth eccentricity in 48 Nepalese alder (*Alnus nepalensis*)
31 trees. This analysis provided data on event timing and magnitudes, average frequency and
32 recurrence interval for reactivation of the study landslide, as well as spatial variability of
33 landslide active. Based on dendrochronological data we were also able to determine the
34 current slope balance and general hazard of landslide reactivation on the study slope. Our

35 study shows that trees and dendrochronology can provide data on the activity of landslides
36 that can complement and improve the results of standard engineering methods. Moreover,
37 dendrochronology itself can provide the full information needed for landslide hazard
38 assessment, monitoring and prediction.

39

40 Keywords: landslide hazard; geohazard prevention; dendrochronology; tree

41 1. Introduction

42 Landslides are particularly destructive geomorphological processes that are often rapid and
43 unpredictable, cause economic and social losses, and directly endanger people, like in 2002,
44 in Nepal, where 16 were killed by a single landslide (Paudel et al., 2003), and in 2011, in
45 Seoul, where landslides resulted in 18 people dead and more than 20 injured (Lee et al., 2020).
46 Other examples of dangerous, catastrophic landslides come from all over the world (e.g.
47 Paolini et al., 2005; Borgatti et al., 2006; Xu et al., 2014; Carey et al., 2015; Wistuba et al.,
48 2019) and include severely damaging, extensive events of massive landslide activation
49 triggered by strong earthquakes (Keefer, 2002) or extreme precipitation (Emberson et al.,
50 2020). Therefore, detecting the occurrence of landslides and landslide-prone slopes,
51 determining the level and background of their activity, assessing landslide hazard and risk,
52 and developing landslide protection and mitigation solutions are among the most important
53 research topics of Earth sciences. These are also important, practical issues for residents of
54 mountain and upland areas. The importance to society and the economy stimulates the
55 constant development of new tools, methods and techniques related to landslide hazard.
56 Currently, a standard set of modern engineering methods dedicated to detecting landslide
57 activity and identifying factors that control it, includes, among all: repeated geodetic and GPS
58 surveys (e.g. Wang et al., 2014; Devoti et al., 2015), inclinometer measurements (e.g. Lollino
59 et al., 2002; Stark and Choi, 2008), piezometer measurements (e.g. Borgatti et al., 2006;
60 Carey et al., 2015) and SAR interferometry (e.g. Casagli et al., 2010; Sun et al., 2015). These
61 engineering methods, besides providing benefits such as high precision of direct
62 measurements of landslide movement, have also limitations. Data from inclinometers and
63 piezometers are often limited to a few measuring points, and sparse in relation to vast
64 landslide surfaces. Moreover, only a short series of measurement data are usually available
65 with all the above-mentioned techniques. The data are limited to the time when the
66 monitoring system was established and rarely reach back more than 20 years (e.g. Wasowski
67 and Pisano, 2020).
68 Short observation periods can hinder the performance of landslide hazard assessments and
69 models, landslide forecasts and thresholds (e.g. Khan et al., 2020). This limitation can be
70 resolved through the reconstruction of past landslide activity from e.g. archival aerial or
71 satellite imagery (Fiorucci et al., 2011). However, for older periods images are often available
72 at irregular intervals of months or years (e.g. Saito et al., 2017) which poses methodological
73 problems. However, another landslide reconstruction method is through dendrochronology,
74 i.e. tree-ring records, as mountain slopes affected by landslides are often completely or

75 partially forested, or provide at least single trees. Dendrochronology offers the advantage of
76 constant annual resolution of data based on annual radial growth rings (e.g. Braam et al.,
77 1987; Schweingruber, 1996), datasets reaching back tens to hundreds of years (Fritts and
78 Swetman, 1986), as well as an opportunity for good spatial resolution of data. In consequence
79 of these unique advantages, dendrochronology has recently become a widely used tool in
80 landslide studies (e.g. Stefanini, 2004; Paolini et al., 2005; Corominas and Moya, 2008; Lopez
81 Saez et al., 2013; Migoń et al., 2014; Šilhán and Stoffel, 2015; Wistuba et al., 2015; Malik et
82 al. 2016; Šilhán, 2017; Oven et al. 2019; Wistuba et al. 2021b).

83 The width and anatomy of every seasonal ring of wood reflect the ontogenetic properties of a
84 certain tree and the conditions of growth in a certain location, in a certain growing season
85 (Fritts and Swetman, 1986), including also ground instability related to landslide activity.
86 Therefore, each single tree can serve as an individual sensor of landsliding and
87 dendrochronology may allow one to overcome the obstacles of direct, engineering methods of
88 landslide monitoring and supplement their results.

89 In the context of ecosystem services landslides and trees were, so far, considered in two ways:
90 Firstly, trees and forests can anchor soil and provide some protection against at least shallow
91 mass movements (Guzzetti et al., 2007; McGuire et al. 2016). Secondly, landslides damage
92 trees and forests, and, consequently, also ecosystem services which they provide. However,
93 the ability of trees and dendrochronology to provide input to landslide risk assessment,
94 monitoring and mitigation (i.e. data on spatiotemporal behaviour and the recurrence of
95 catastrophic landslides in the past, and contemporary balance of slopes – e.g. Wistuba et al.,
96 2019) should also be considered an ecosystem service itself. Thus, this study aims to explore
97 and present the potential of trees in providing landslide-monitoring ecosystem services
98 through dendrochronology. In particular, we aim to present the potential for the following
99 ecosystem services: (i) determining the temporal and spatial variability of landslide events,
100 (ii) determining the related level of landslide hazard and (iii) detecting initial landslide
101 movements preceding catastrophic events. Finally, we aim to establish a concept of landslide-
102 monitoring ecosystem service. In our opinion, recognizing this concept and exploring it is
103 even more important under the current conditions of changing climate which intensify
104 geohazards of various origins, including landslides, up to previously unobserved magnitudes
105 and frequencies (Haque et al., 2019).

106

107
 108 Fig. 1. The location of the landslide under study in the Moxi River basin, Sichuan Province,
 109 China (A), its relief and distribution of *Alnus nepalensis* trees sampled for the
 110 dendrochronological analysis (B).

111
 112 2. Materials and methods

113
 114 2.1 Study landslide

115 The study landslide is located in Sichuan, China, in the basin of Moxi River, Yangtze
 116 catchment (29.700896° N, 102.089005° E) (Fig. 1). The Moxi basin drains the eastern part of
 117 the Gongga Shan massif (max 7556 m a.s.l.), the highest part of the Hengduan Mts. on the
 118 south-eastern edge of the Qinghai-Tibet Plateau bordering the Sichuan Basin. The bedrock of
 119 the Moxi basin is mainly composed of crystalline rocks, and Permian granites in the case of
 120 study landslide. The bedrock is covered with a thick mantle of regolith, loamy, poorly sorted
 121 glacial and mass-movement deposits (Tie, 2013). The area lies at the junction of three major
 122 faults of Southwestern China (Ni et al., 2010) with significant seismic activity, numerous
 123 earthquakes (including the disastrous 2008 Wenchuan earthquake, M 8.0 – Xu et al., 2014)
 124 and an annual uplift rate of c 2 mm (Clark et al., 2004). The Moxi basin has a semi-humid,

125 mountain climate with cool, wet summers and cold, dry winters. The annual average
126 temperature in the area is 6.8°C and the annual average precipitation total is 1937 mm. The
127 precipitation, however, distinctly increases with terrain altitude, up to 3000 mm per year (Ni
128 et al., 2010). The majority of rainfall falls during summer (June-September), south-eastern
129 monsoon which also brings floods (Li et al., 2010), hazardous fluvial erosion and
130 accumulation, and mass movements, including debris flows and landslides (Su and Shi,
131 2002). The landslide under study is elongated: 1150 m long and only 190 m wide in its middle
132 section. It is a shallow, complex landslide developed in the Pleistocene-Holocene glacial
133 moraine deposits at the side of the main Moxi valley. Its relief is mostly typical for flow-type
134 landslides, but there are also some backwards rotated blocks in the middle section. The
135 landslide surface is steep with c 600 m difference between the landslide crown and toe eroded
136 by the main channel of the Moxi valley (Fig. 1). The landslide surface is covered with
137 Nepalese alder (*Alnus nepalensis*) forest, Faber's oak (*Quercus fabrei*) thickets and few
138 juvenile Shensi firs (*Abies chensiensis*).

139

140

141 Fig. 2. Growth eccentricity developed in stems of deciduous trees tilted by landslide activity:
142 in the downslope (A) and upslope direction (B), and concentric growth of trees with straight
143 stems, unaffected by landslide activity (C).

144

145

146 Fig. 3. Dating landslide events from tree-ring eccentricity developed in a stem of *Alnus*
 147 *nepalensis* tree tilted downslope on the studied landslide.

148

149 2.2 Methods of the study

150 Dendrochronological analysis of landslide activity is based on the anatomical reaction of trees
 151 to slope instability. The instability causes tilting and bending of tree stems (Fig. 2) resulting in
 152 mechanical strains and the development of datable anatomical features (Shroder, 1978),
 153 including tree-ring eccentricity (Braam et al., 1987) (Fig. 2). Growth eccentricity occurs when
 154 growth intensity is uneven within the stem perimeter. It is the tendency of a tree to develop
 155 wider rings on one side of the stem. In the case of deciduous trees, such as *Alnus nepalensis*
 156 sampled on the studied landslide, the growth is more intensive and the rings are wider on the
 157 upper side of a tilted stem (Timell, 1986).

158 We have collected dendrochronological samples (i.e. increment cores) from specimens of the
 159 Nepalese alder (*Alnus nepalensis*) growing on the studied landslide (Fig. 1). For the sampling,
 160 we selected trees with uninjured stems, no visible health issues and crown damages. In total,
 161 we sampled increment cores from 48 alder trees growing on the study landslide and 10 trees
 162 growing on the reference, stable slope, 800 m NW from the study landslide. Trees sampled on

163 the reference slope were used in reference threshold calculation (Wistuba et al., 2013) (Fig.
164 3). We collected samples using Pressler borers, at the breast height of each tree. Two cores
165 were extracted per tree, parallel to the slope inclination: one from the upslope side of the tree
166 stem and another from the downslope side. In the laboratory, the cores were glued into
167 wooden holders and sanded using sandpaper of increasing grit (100, 250, 500 and 1000).
168 Then, tree-ring widths were measured with an accuracy of 0.01 mm using a LinTab
169 measurement station. Based on the comparison of tree-ring widths measured on opposite sides
170 of a single tree stem, the eccentricity index and its yearly variation were calculated (Wistuba
171 et al., 2013) (Fig. 3). Events of landslide activity on the studied slope were dated based on the
172 yearly variation compared against the reference thresholds (Fig. 3). The reference thresholds
173 represent average levels of yearly variation on the reference, stable slope, calculated
174 separately for the years with increases of the eccentricity index (a threshold for positive
175 variation values: 106.04 per cent points) and for the years with its decreases (a threshold for
176 negative variation values: - 91.79 per cent points).
177 Finally, we calculated the total amount of trees disturbed by landslide activity (i.e. trees with
178 dated events of eccentricity) in each calendar year on each landslide. We also calculated the
179 response index, which is the percentage of trees disturbed by landslide activity in each
180 particular year in proportion to the total number of sampled trees already growing in the same
181 year (sample depth value) (Shroder Jr, 1978). For each sampled tree we also determined the
182 mean frequency of landslide events, i.e. the average number of landslide events per decade.
183 Based on these values we developed maps of spatial variability of landslide activity and
184 landslide hazard using ArcGIS software and the “Spline with Barriers” interpolation tool. We
185 also checked the variability of the eccentricity index in each sampled tree in search of
186 eccentricity escalations recording a recent increase in ground instability, and therefore
187 increase in the risk for landslide reactivation, according to the concept presented by Wistuba
188 et al. (2019).

189

190 3. Results

191

192 3.1 Temporal variability of landslide activity

193 The dendrochronological record for the study landslide has been available since 1975, as the
194 oldest sampled tree dates back to this year (Fig. 4). Therefore, the whole period available for
195 the analysis covers 47 years. However, the majority of sampled 48 trees started to grow in the
196 1980s. Sample depth exceeds 50% (>24 sampled trees) since 1985 (Fig. 4). This provides 37

197 years of the most reliable data on the activity of the study landslide, a period sufficiently long
198 for hazard estimations.

199 The oldest event of landslide activity in the sampled trees (i.e. eccentricity developed in
200 reaction to stem tilting by ground instability) was dated in 1981 (Fig. 4). Since then, landslide
201 events have been dated in almost all calendar years. In single years we have dated landslide
202 activity in 1-26 of sampled trees. In total, in all years and all sampled trees we have dated 441
203 events of eccentricity developed in reaction to landslide activity. Among these events, there is
204 a balance between upslope eccentricity (52%) and downslope eccentricity (48%) which
205 reflects the balance between downslope and upslope directions of tree tilting on the study
206 landslide, and corresponds with the relief of studied landslide, typical for flow-type
207 landslides, and the significant steepness of the studied slope.

208

209

210 Fig. 4. Results of dendrochronological dating of the activity of landslide under study: number
211 of trees with ring eccentricity events compared to the sample depth.

212

213 The number of trees with dendrochronological records of landslide activity (i.e. dated growth
214 eccentricity) varies between calendar years (Figs. 4 and 5). This temporal variability is best
215 represented by response index values (Fig. 5), a dendrochronological proxy of landslide
216 activity. In general, the higher the value of the response index, the more intensive and more
217 widespread landslide movements occurred on the study slope in a certain year. The highest
218 values of the response index were obtained for 2005 (54.17%), 2009 (52.08%), 2006, 2020
219 and 2021 (45.83% each year), 2018 (43.75%) and 2014 (41.67%). The above-average values
220 of the response index were found in 1986, 1993-1995, 1997-1998, 2001-2003, 2005-2006,
221 2009-2015 and 2017-2021 (Fig. 5). Thus, the study landslide presented above-average activity

222 over the majority of the last 20-30 years. We have also identified 14 major events of landslide
 223 activity for the whole study landslide based on above-average values of the response index
 224 and year-by-year changes of the index value (years with increases up to the above-average
 225 values were considered events) (Fig. 5). This gives an average of 3 events per 10 years and
 226 recurrence interval of 3.33 years.
 227

228
 229 Fig. 5. Response index values (per cent of disturbed trees in the sample population) in 1975-
 230 2021 for the study landslide compared to the average response index value (20.21%), along
 231 with dated events of landslide activity.

232 233 3.2 Spatial variability of landslide activity

234 The number of dated eccentricity events varies significantly among 48 studied trees, from
 235 none up to 17. The number of events dated in each single tree depends on the local activity of
 236 landslide at the sampling spot, but also the age of a tree. Thus, to make the results
 237 comparable, in the analysis of spatial variability of landslide activity we analysed data only
 238 for the period when all sampled trees were already growing, i.e. since 1995 (Fig. 4). During
 239 these 27 years, the total number of eccentricity events in single sampled trees varied from 0 to
 240 15, which amounts for an average frequency of 0-5.56 events per 10 years. This indicates that
 241 in the most active sampling spots ground instability can occur every two years on average,
 242 while some parts of the landslide body remain completely stable. However, the mean
 243 frequency calculated for all 48 sampled trees remains high, 3.01 events per 100 years, similar
 244 to the median (3.33), which indicates very frequent landslide reactivation (every 3 years).

245 The average frequency of landslide reactivation varies over the studied slope (Fig. 6). The
 246 highest frequency has been found for the middle section of the landslide under study, in
 247 particular at its southern boundary, along a deep through of a rockfall track remodelled by
 248 water erosion (Figs. 1 and 6). All sampled trees showing the average frequency of landsliding
 249 over 4 events per 10 years grow in this area (Fig. 6). The increased instability of this part of
 250 the landslide during the last three decades may, in fact, result from erosion occurring within
 251 the rockfall track which debutresses the landslide body. The remaining part of the studied
 252 slope is significantly less active (Fig. 6). The least active part of the studied slope is its
 253 uppermost section, below the landslide headscarp (Fig. 6) which suggests that the instability
 254 recorded in the sampled trees during the last 30 years are most likely secondary movements
 255 that do not affect the main sheer surface of the landslide.

256

257

258 Fig. 6. Average frequency of landslide events dated from sampled trees in 1995-2021 (A),
 259 interpolated map of the average frequency of landslide events (B) and distribution of trees
 260 with dendrochronological record of ongoing landslide movements (eccentricity escalations)
 261 (C).

262

263 3.3 Assessment of the contemporary slope balance

264 We checked the variability of the eccentricity index in each sampled tree in search for
 265 eccentricity escalations lasting at least three years in a row and continuing until 2021, which
 266 would record ongoing landslide movements posing a risk of future landslide catastrophe (e.g.
 267 Fig. 7). Among 48 sampled trees we found only five specimens fulfilling aforesaid conditions
 268 of eccentricity escalation (Fig. 6). Although some of the remaining 43 sampled trees present
 269 dated event of landslide activity in the last years before sampling, do not show signs of
 270 continuous, ongoing eccentricity escalation (e.g. Fig. 3), thus, they do not indicate the hazard
 271 of catastrophic landslide reactivation in the near future. Among the five trees with eccentricity
 272 escalations, four grow on one landslide block, in the area already determined as the most
 273 active part of the studied slope (Fig. 6). This indicates that the risk of landslide reactivation on
 274 the studied slope is minor and concerns only a small part of it, a landslide block laterally
 275 undermined by linear erosion occurring within a rockfall track (Fig. 1).
 276

277
 278 Fig. 7. An example of continuous, ongoing escalation of eccentricity index in a tree sampled
 279 on the studied landslide – an indicator of contemporary ground instability and future hazard of
 280 landslide reactivation.

281
 282 4. Discussion

283 Due to the formation of annual rings of wood and features of wood anatomy, such as the
284 eccentricity of radial growth, trees can be useful in indicating landslide hazard.
285 Dendrochronological dating allows the reconstruction of landslide events over the last
286 decades and centuries, but also the monitoring of the current slope balance (Wistuba et al.,
287 2019). It is often assumed that coniferous tree species are more advantageous than deciduous
288 for dendrogeomorphological analyses of landslides. Hence, the conifers are more often used
289 for the purpose. This is because they develop more clear ring boundaries and compression
290 wood (Timell, 1986) which is relatively easy to identify and can also be used in dating
291 landslide activity (e.g. Wistuba et al., 2021b). However, dating landslide activity from growth
292 eccentricity gives more potential, thanks to the fact that eccentricity can easily be measured
293 and recalculated, contrary to reaction wood (compression wood in conifers and tension wood
294 in deciduous species), which is mainly dated visually. Data on tree-ring eccentricity, on the
295 other hand, can be processed and presented mathematically, and provide not only the time of
296 tree reaction to landslide activity but also the magnitude of this reaction. This measurability of
297 growth eccentricity allows for the dendrochronological monitoring of current slope balance
298 and prediction of future catastrophic landslide reactivation (based on eccentricity escalation –
299 Wistuba et al., 2019) which would not be possible based on reaction wood.

300 Based on the dendrochronological analysis of tree-ring eccentricity among 48 specimens of
301 deciduous Nepalese alder (*Alnus nepalensis*) growing in the Moxi basin, Sichuan, China, we
302 determined the level of the activity of studied landslide in the past, i.e. landslide frequency
303 and past magnitudes. Importantly, we were able to determine the years when the study
304 landslide was most active in the past, which potentially can also allow us to determine the
305 factors controlling the activity of the study landslide, i.e. its triggering factors (e.g. Wistuba et
306 al., 2021b). It is already clear that some of the years when the highest values of the response
307 index were obtained (Fig. 5) match the occurrence of intensive precipitation or earthquakes,
308 including the 2008 Wenchuan earthquake (e.g. Xu et al., 2014) and 2020 extreme
309 precipitation and floods in the Yangtze basin (e.g. Wang et al., 2021). Obtained data on
310 landslide activity in the past, if compared with detailed data on potential landslide triggers,
311 can become an input to more complex statistical analysis leading to the calculation of
312 threshold levels of precipitation and earthquakes necessary for landslide reactivation (e.g.
313 Wistuba et al., 2021a). Conducted dendrochronological dating and the following analysis
314 allowed us also to determine the average frequency of landslide events on the studied slope (3
315 events per 10 years) and the recurrence interval for reactivation of the study landslide (c 3-3,5

316 years). Such data on landslide triggers, frequency and magnitudes are important for estimating
317 landslide hazard and risk, and landslide activity prediction.

318 Furthermore, the spatial analysis of dendrochronological data provided information on the
319 most and the least active parts of the study landslide. Such data on the variability of landslide
320 activity over a slope or a mountain massif are crucial for spatial planning and land-use
321 management in landslide-affected areas (e.g. Lopez Saez et al., 2013; Łuszczynska et al.,
322 2019). Based on dendrochronological data we were also able to determine the general hazard
323 of landslide reactivation on the study slope and determine that the instability recorded in the
324 sampled trees during the last 30 years is most likely secondary movements. We determined
325 the current slope balance and found that the present risk of catastrophic landslide reactivation
326 on the studied slope is minor and concerns only a small part of it, a particular landslide block
327 being subject to erosional debulking. However, once this landslide block slides downslope,
328 the balance of the whole slope will change and further behaviour of the rest of the landslide
329 body remains unknown. There are examples of major landslide reactivations which began
330 with the reactivation of smaller landforms, e.g. landslide toes eroded by river channels.

331 The presented example of the landslide studied in the Moxi basin, China, proves that
332 dendrochronology can provide the full information needed for landslide hazard assessment,
333 monitoring and prediction, three elements of the proposed new ecosystem service based on
334 the ability of trees to record ground instability. The new ecosystem service could be a subject
335 of social and economic valuation. As the economic costs of landslides are often significant
336 they are the subject of calculations based on actual losses during catastrophic events, but also
337 based on the value of infrastructure (roads, power grid, water supply network, buildings,
338 housing facilities, public services such as schools, hospitals etc.) located within the range of
339 landslide impact, potentially endangered by destruction due landslide reactivation. Economic
340 costs of landslide activity also include evacuation costs, construction of alternative and
341 temporary communication routes, power, water and gas supply grid, and alternative,
342 temporary accommodation. Social costs of landslides are also measurable and include
343 fatalities, injuries and traumas. Economic valuation of the new ecosystem service of
344 dendrochronological landslide monitoring could also be calculated based on the costs of
345 alternative, standard engineering methods of landslide monitoring (e.g. inclinometer
346 measurements), which are often costly and time-consuming, compared to tree-ring analyses.

347 In our opinion, the practical aspect of dendrochronological analyses of landslides is
348 promising, considering the advantages of the method and the opportunities given by tree
349 biology, but it has long been overlooked. It has been emphasized only recently. Thus,

350 establishing the new proposed ecosystem service would help promote empirical evidence on
351 the efficiency of tree-ring-based tools to decision-makers and support its mainstreaming into
352 landslide management policies.

353 The efficiency of trees and dendrochronology in providing the ecosystem service of landslide
354 monitoring is provided by methodological restrictions related mainly to sampled tree stand.
355 The analyses should be conducted and the data should be interpreted with particular concern
356 to issues related to tree age and the age structure of sampled tree stand. The older the trees,
357 the longer the period available for landslide analysis and the better the reliability of results.
358 Sampling juvenile trees is also unsuitable from the biological, methodological point of view.
359 Another issue of concern is the number of sampled trees and their distribution over a studied
360 landslide. Landslide activity often varies in space, even at a local scale. Different parts of one
361 landslide can present different levels of activity. Therefore, the more trees are sampled on a
362 study slope, the more accurate the hazard analysis. The selection of trees for sampling is also
363 vital as they should be healthy, without stem injuries and damages to the crown, i.e.
364 assimilation apparatus. Restrictions related to tree health may in some cases severely limit the
365 possibility of collecting a suitable number of samples at a study site.

366

367 5. Conclusions

368 1. Dendrochronological analysis of growth eccentricity among Nepalese alder (*Alnus*
369 *nepalensis*) trees allowed us to determine landslide frequency and past magnitudes on the
370 study slope in the Moxi basin, Sichuan, China. We also determined the average frequency of
371 3 landslide events per 10 years and the recurrence interval of 3.33 years for reactivation of the
372 study landslide. Based on the spatial analysis of dendrochronological data we also determined
373 the most active and the least active parts of the study landslide.

374 2. Results of tree-ring-based analysis provided data on the activity of the study landslide
375 which are comparable to data provided by standard engineering methods. Moreover, some
376 information provided by dendrochronology (such as several decades-long datasets on
377 landslide activity) is unique, and would not be available with any other method.

378 3. Dendrochronological data on landslide frequency and magnitudes obtained in this study are
379 crucial for estimating landslide hazard and risk, and landslide activity prediction. Data on
380 spatial variability of landslide activity over the study slope can serve in spatial planning and
381 land-use management. Dendrochronological data on landslide activity can serve as a basis for
382 determining triggering factors controlling the activity of the study landslide. I.e., they can
383 become an input for the calculation of threshold levels of precipitation and earthquakes

384 necessary for landslide reactivation. Moreover, our results show that dendrochronological
385 analysis conducted at an early stage of research can improve the performance of landslide
386 models and provide valuable input to any type of slope stability modelling.

387 4. Based on dendrochronological data we were also able to determine the current slope
388 balance and general hazard of landslide reactivation on the study slope. We established
389 that over the last 30 years, the study landslide was most likely subject to secondary
390 movements, and the present risk of catastrophic reactivation is minor and concerns only one
391 of the landslide blocks.

392 5. Results obtained for the study landslide in the Moxi basin, Sichuan, China, prove that
393 dendrochronology can provide the full information needed for landslide hazard assessment,
394 monitoring and prediction, three elements of the proposed a new ecosystem service based on
395 the ability of trees to record ground instability. Establishing the new proposed ecosystem
396 service would help promote empirical evidence on the efficiency of tree-ring-based tools to
397 decision-makers and support its mainstreaming into landslide management policies.

398

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